

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furo-coumarins ; Part XIX*. Synthesis of 4-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene.

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2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenyl acetophenone on allylation gave 4-allyloxy derivative, which on condensation with diethyl carbonate furnished 4-hydroxy-3-phenyl-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin (Ia). Methylation, followed by Claisen rearrangement of (Ia) gave the corresponding 6-allyl compound, which on cyclisation followed by dehydrogenation gave 4-methoxy- and 4-hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene.

IN continuation of our work in the synthesis of 4-hydroxypsoralene derivatives,¹ we report here the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene⁺.

2, 4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenyl acetophenone² was allylated with allyl bromide to give 4-allyloxy-3-methyl-2-hydroxy- ω -phenylacetophenone, which on condensation with diethyl carbonate in the presence of sodium³, gave 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-4-hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin (Ia). The I. R. Spectrum of (Ia) showed a band in the carbonyl region viz. 1655 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group) and a band at 930 cm^{-1} ($=\text{CH}_2$ group). The low $\text{C}=\text{O}$ frequency is due to hydrogen bonding⁴ in 4-hydroxycoumarin. (Ia) was methylated to 4-methoxy derivative (Ib), which on Claisen rearrangement gave three products as shown by T. L. C. The separation of the mixture was affected by treating the ethereal solution of the mixture first with sodium bicarbonate and then with sodium hydroxide solution. Evaporation of the ether gave the product, which was insoluble either in sodium bicarbonate or sodium hydroxide solution and was found to be original compound (Ib). Acidification of the sodium bicarbonate extract gave 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin(Ia), indicating that demethylation took place during the reaction. Acidification of the sodium hydroxide extract gave 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-methoxycoumarin (Ic). The compound (Ic) on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid, gave two products. The compound which was soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution has been assigned 4-hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethyl-4', 5'-dihydropsoresalene (IIa) structure^{6,7}; while the other compound, which was insoluble either in sodium bicarbonate or in sodium hydroxide solution has been assigned 4-methoxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethyl-4', 5'-dihydropsoresalene (IIb) structure. The formation of (IIa) indicated that demethylation took place during cyclisation⁵. The structures (IIa) and (IIb) are supported by I. R. Spectra which showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz. 1640 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group) respectively. Compound (IIa) was methylated and was found to be identical with the

compound (IIb) by mixed m. p. determination. Dehydrogenation of (IIb) with palladised charcoal (10%) also gave a mixture of two compounds, which was separated by fractional crystallisation from benzene. These have been assigned 4-hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene(IIIa) and 4-methoxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIb) structure, on the basis of their solubilities in alkali.

I a: R = R₁ = -H; R₂ = -CH₂-CH=CH₂
 b: R = -CH₃; R₁ = -H; R₂ = -CH₂-CH=CH₂
 c: R = -CH₃; R₁ = -CH₂-CH=CH₂; R₂ = -H

II a: R = -H
 b: R = -CH₃

III a: R = -H
 b: R = -CH₃
 [Fig. 1.]

(IIa), on dehydrogenation, gave a compound which was identical with (IIIa) by mixed m. p. determination. Formation of (IIIa) from (IIb) indicated that demethylation also took place during dehydrogenation. (IIIa) on methylation gave (IIIb). The U. V. Spectra of (IIIa) are recorded to study the structure and the photodynamic activity.

Experimental

I. R. spectra are determined with Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer in nujol.

The ultra-violet absorption spectra are measured with Beckmann DU spectrophotometer in ethanol.

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (Ia): A solution of 4-allyloxy-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-*o*-phenylacetophenone (2 g.) in diethyl carbonate (15 ml.) was carefully added to pulverised sodium (2 g.) and the mixture was heated in a water bath for 6 hrs. After cooling the excess of sodium was decomposed by slow addition of alcohol (25 ml.). The contents were poured into ice water and ether extracted to remove unreacted compounds. The alkaline aqueous layer on acidification gave the product, which after filtration was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution. The solution was filtered and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated product after filtration crystallised from benzene, m. p. 213°. Yield 2 g. (Found: C, 74.32; H, 5.01. $C_{19}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 74.01; H, 5.19%).

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-methoxycoumarin (Ib): A mixture of 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-hydroxy-coumarin (2 g.), dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.) and anhydrous Potassium carbonate (8 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml.) in a water bath for 5 hrs. Acetone was evaporated and the residue was treated with water. The separated product was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove unreacted compound. The product was dried and crystallised from benzene, m. p. 134°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 74.42; H, 5.49. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.52; H, 5.59%).

6-Allyl-7,8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-methoxycoumarin (Ic): 7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-methoxycoumarin (2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (12 ml.) for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid (25 ml.) containing crushed ice. The compound was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was first shaken with sodium bicarbonate solution. The aqueous layer was separated and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 213°. This compound was found to be 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (Ia). Their mixed m. p. was not depressed.

Further, the ethereal layer was shaken with sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline layer was separated and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 178°. Yield 1 g. (Found: C, 74.64; H, 5.48. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.52; H, 5.59%).

The ether extract after evaporation of the ether gave little amount of (Ib).

4-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethyl-4', 5-dihydro-psoralene (IIa) and 4-methoxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethyl-4', 5'-dihydro-psoralene (IIb): 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3-phenyl-4-methoxycoumarin (1 g) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (8 ml.) in a water bath for 15 mins. The mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The solution was filtered and the residue was found to be (IIb). It crystallised from alcohol m. p. 192°. Yield 0.4 g. The compound (IIb) was insoluble in sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: C, 74.42; H, 5.53. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.52; H, 5.59%.)

The filtrate was acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid and the separated product was filtered and was found to be (IIa). It crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 220. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 73.91; H, 5.14. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.01; H, 5.29%.)

The compound (IIa) was methylated to (IIb) by dimethyl sulphate in acetone solution.

4-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIa) and 4-Methoxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethylpsoralene (IIIb): A mixture of 4-methoxy-3-phenyl-5', 8-dimethyl-4', 5'-dihydro-psoralene (0.5 g.), palladised charcoal (0.3 g.; 10%) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (4 ml.) for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was filtered hot. After cooling, petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. The product was tested on T. L. C. and it was found to be a mixture of two compounds. The mixture was separated by treatment with hot benzene. The insoluble product was found to be (IIIa). It crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 260°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 74.74; H, 4.56. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.50; H, 4.57%). λ_{max} (ethanol) 240 nm (10g. ϵ 4.30); 315 (3.95).

The benzene extract on cooling gave the compound which was filtered off. The filtrate on concentration and cooling gave pure compound (IIIb), which recrystallised from benzene, m. p. 163°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 74.94; H, 4.95. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 75.00; H, 5.00%).

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References

- *Part XVIII. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 41.
- Nomenclature used in this paper is according to A. CURTIUS, *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1959, 32, 133.
- V. N. DHOLAKIA and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1058.
- N. H. PARDANANI and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1035.
- J. BOYD and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 174.
- P. W. HUTEHISON and J. A. TOMBLISON, *Tetrahedron*, 1969, 25, 2531.
- N. J. DESAI and S. SETHNA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 358.
- N. H. PARDANANI and K. N. TRIVEDI, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 1537.
- Y. A. SHAIKH and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 41.